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Milestones in Physics (27)

Developments for the FCC-ee vacuum system

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Abstract

The Future Circular Collider (FCC), the proposed next large CERN's accelerator, would realize a groundbreaking high-energy physics research initiative following the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) successes. This study emphasizes the vacuum system's pivotal role in reducing radiation effects, beam instabilities, and maintaining low-pressure conditions, essential for optimal electron-positron collider performance.

Intense optimization and prototyping efforts are required in the future years, together with tight collaboration with the industry.

1. Introduction

CERN's Large Hadron Collider (LHC) is presently full steam in its third operational run (run-3) colliding two beams of protons at 13.6 TeV at the centre of mass and Pb ions at 2.7 TeV/nucleon. At the end of this run, planned in 2026, the world largest accelerator will undergo a major upgrade that aims to increase the proton collision rate, namely its luminosity [1]. This improvement will be attained by installing new equipment, notably new Nb₃Sn superconducting final focusing magnets, during the Long Shutdown 3 (LS3) that will last three years. The final goal of this project (High Luminosity LHC, HL-LHC) is to accumulate by the early forties an integrated luminosity of 3000 fb⁻¹ (i.e., ten times more than that obtained in an equivalent time of operation from 2010 to 2023) ¹ [2]. When such a high collection of events will be available, the discovery potential of the LHC will be exhausted, therefore requiring a new facility to pursue the quest of fundamental laws of the Universe.

As high-energy particle accelerators need at least two decades from the conceptual proposal to start of operation, CERN and several worldwide collaborators are already working on design and feasibility studies for a new 91 km circumference (see Fig. 1) accelerator featuring in a first step an electron-positron collider, and then a hadron-hadron one with a centre-of-mass energy of 100 TeV (i.e., 7 times that of the LHC) [3]. This study is named *Future Circular Collider* (FCC); today, it is considered as the highest-priority next collider by the European Strategy for Particle Physics (ESPP) [4].

The FCC feasibility study should be completed in 2025 for the next ESPP update around 2026. It mainly focusses on the civil engineering infrastructure and its impact on the local area. Moreover, it aims to optimize the design of the main ring and its injection chain, including the development of crucial equipment and their environmental and sustainability aspects. Finally and importantly, a consolidated cost estimate is being prepared together with a funding model [5].

Staging electron-positron collisions (FCC-ee) first and then hadron-hadron ones (FCC-hh) in the same tunnel is the best option. In addition to the physics prospects, this choice optimizes the cost of the infrastructure, as was the case with the Large Electron Positron collider, LEP, which was later replaced by the LHC in the same tunnel [5]. Furthermore, this choice gives enough time for the development of new affordable superconducting magnets (e.g., using Nb₃Sn and

Fig. 1: Schematic views of the FCC-ee accelerator (90.7 km long) and its indicative geographical implantation. The scheme shows in green the booster (not to scale), where the electron and positron bunches are accelerated, and in blue the storage rings, where the two beams circulate in opposite direction in separate beampipes except in the four interaction points where collisions take place. Courtesy of M. Benedikt, J. Gutleber and V. Mertens (CERN).

¹ An integrated luminosity of 1 fb⁻¹ is equivalent to roughly 10¹⁴ proton-proton collisions [6].

high- T_c superconducting cables) delivering magnetic fields in the range 16 to 20 T to steer 50 TeV protons in the FCC-hh.

Contrary to FCC-hh, FCC-ee is technologically mature. Despite that, dedicated development is mandatory to optimize essential systems, like normal-conducting magnets, collimation, vacuum, and RF acceleration, and to minimize costs and electricity consumption. In this latter respect, a ceiling to the maximum power lost per beam in synchrotron radiation is limited to 50 MW, which in turn sets boundaries to the maximum beam current at a given beam energy.

In the present projected schedule, the civil engineering work for the FCC would start in the thirties for beginning of operation with electrons and positrons about 15 years later.

The FCC-ee operation involves four phases (see Tab. 1), each targeting a defined scientific objective. The first phase, the one at the lowest energy, aims to generate as much as possible Z bosons². The beam energy and current are 45.6 GeV (≈ 91 GeV at the centre of mass) and 1.27 A, respectively, carried by 11200 bunches of 2.14×10^{11} electrons or positrons. The last phase, with the most energetic beams (182.5 GeV, 4.9 mA), is dedicated to the study of top quarks. In the two intermediate energy steps, FCC-ee runs as a W^\pm and H(ZH) facility. Recently, some experimentalists have proposed an alternative operation scenario where FCC-ee would start its operation at the ZH energy, as shown in Fig. 2.

² The Z and W^\pm bosons are fundamental particles that carry the weak nuclear force. The weak force is responsible for certain types of radioactive decays and interactions involving particles like electrons and neutrinos. H indicates the Higgs boson. Z bosons generated by proton collisions can interact with the Higgs field, giving rise to the creation of a Higgs boson because of this interaction (ZH).

Fig. 2: Integrated luminosity, expressed in inverse attobarn, along the operational years of the FCC-ee. In this scenario, the FCC-ee would initially operate as a Higgs boson facility [7].

Parameters	Z	W^+W^-	H (ZH)	$t - \bar{t}$
Beam energy [GeV]	45.6	80	120	182.5
Beam current [mA]	1270	137	26.7	4.9
Number of bunches / beam	11200	1780	440	60
Bunch intensity [$\times 10^{11}$]	2.14	1.45	1.15	1.55
Luminosity per detector [$\times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$]	140	20	5.0	1.25
Years of operation	4	2	3	5
Particle produced	5×10^{12}	$> 10^8 W^+W^-$	$2 \times 10^6 H$	$2 \times 10^6 t\bar{t}$ pairs
FCC-ee / LEP [10]	10^6	10^4	/	/

Table 1: Main parameters of the FCC-ee beams in the four different energy phases [5]. FCC-ee / LEP gives the figures of the FCC-ee with respect to the LEP. ' \bar{t} ' is the antimatter counterpart of the top quark 't'.

In the present design, the FCC-ee accelerator consists of two rings, where positrons and electrons counter rotate, placed side-by-side at a distance of 350 mm along the arcs. A full-energy booster ring capable to inject into the two rings e^- and e^+ in opposite directions is placed 1300 mm above the two storage rings. Four interaction points, IP, where the two beams cross their path and collide at a small angle (30 mrad), and related detectors are presently expected.

2. Vacuum requirements

The main objective of the vacuum system is to **ensure that the beam-gas scattering lifetime** is large enough not to be detrimental to the integrated luminosity. This criterium fixes a limit to the average pressure in the low 10^{-9} mbar range in the beampipe of the storage rings of the FCC-ee when beams circulate. The residual gas species should be mostly H_2 , with CH_4 , CO and CO_2 about one order of magnitude lower. The partial pressures of gas species with molecular masses above 44 must be negligible.

Another important objective of the vacuum system is **reducing or even eliminating the electron cloud** [8] and **ion-trapping effects** [9] and related beam instabilities and losses. The first detrimental mechanism affects positively charged beams. As bunched high-energy particle beams traverse the vacuum chamber, electrons can be emitted from and accelerated towards the beampipe walls. If the secondary electron yield of the inner surfaces is higher than a given threshold, a multipacting mechanism is generated with possible impact on beam dynamics. Photoelectrons emitted by synchrotron radiation also contribute significantly to the electron cloud formation. Ion-trapping instabilities impact the quality of negatively charged beams. They occur when positively charged ions, generated by beam-gas interactions, get trapped in the beam's potential, leading to an accumulation around the beam itself. These trapped ions can cause significant beam degradation. In both cases, instabilities can result in beam loss, emittance growth (beam size and divergence), and other undesirable effects, that could spoil the performance of such a complex accelerator.

While the first two objectives apply in all positions of the main FCC-ee ring, a third fundamental one concerns the interfaces between the four particle detectors and the accelerator, i.e. the fraction of accelerator nearby and inside the detectors, frequently referred to as Machine-Detector Interfaces (MDI). In these specific cases, the vacuum chambers must be designed to reduce as much as possible the radiation background reaching the detector. As it is explained in detail in the next chapters, five sources of radiation background can be accounted for, including inelastic beam gas scattering and beam emitted synchrotron radiation.

3. Synchrotron radiation

Synchrotron radiation (hereafter SR), a relativistic effect resulting in the emission of electromagnetic waves by a

charged particle moving in a magnetic field [10], characterizes so strongly the design and performance of the FCC-ee vacuum system that, in this context, it deserves particular consideration.

SR has been observed first by astrophysicists who called it “magnetic breaking radiation”, or “magnetic bremsstrahlung”. In accelerators it was first noticed in a small tabletop synchrotron run by the General Electric Corp. in Schenectady, NY, USA, in the early 50s. Its physical explanation has been given by Julian Schwinger, Nobel prize in physics for studies in quantum electrodynamics, in the western world, and independently by Sokolov and Ternov in the USSR. The generation and use of SR has been greatly enhanced later by a class of accelerators known as “light sources”, which nowadays constitute a large fraction of the research accelerators worldwide (for example, the Swiss Light Source at the Paul Scherrer Institute).

SR is characterized by a continuous spectrum ranging from microwaves to hard gamma rays, depending on the energy of the charged beam, its charge, mass, and magnetic field strength. One of the main figures of merit of SR is the critical energy, ε_c , which divides the spectrum in two parts, equally splitting the emitted power. The critical energy depends on the third power of the beam energy and is inversely proportional to the radius of curvature of the orbit. Typically, SR is generated along dipole magnets, where the beam trajectory follows an arc of circumference. Along the ring, dipoles are separated by straight sections where quadrupole magnets are inserted, in order to focus the electron (or positron) beams. Quadrupoles too generate SR emission, but with lower intensity as compared to dipoles, except in the very particular area of the MDI where stronger superconducting quadrupoles are used to squeeze the colliding beams. In those four locations, the strength of the focusing quadrupoles is very high, the so called “gradient” (units are T/m). Higher order magnets, like sextupoles and octupoles, although needed, they generate a negligible amount of SR.

SR can induce desorption of gas molecules from the inner beampipe surfaces whenever the critical energy raises above the few eV range [11]. This effect is called “photon-stimulated desorption” (PSD). In FCC-ee, as in modern synchrotron light sources, it is the main source of gas in the accelerator’s vacuum system. Protons generate SR as well, even if the total emitted power is inversely proportional to the fourth power of the mass of the particle (1836^4 times lower as compared to electrons on the same orbit and energy). This is well known at CERN from LHC operation: as soon as the proton beam energy is ramped up above 2 TeV, pressure rises in locations where photons are expected to impinge [12].

Fig. 3 shows the SR flux spectra of the FCC-ee in four operational phases compared to a known light source, the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility in Grenoble, a 6 GeV 200 mA electron storage ring. One table on the figure gives the value of the critical energy ε_c of each spectrum. The other table gives the linear photon flux generated by 1 m of beam trajectory along a dipole.

We can see that the ESRF has a larger SR photon flux at low photon energies, while the FCC-ee has larger critical

Fig. 3: SR spectra for four FCC-ee energies and the ESRF; B.W. means “Band Width”. The two embedded tables report the critical energies and the number of photons generated per metre of orbit per second in the five cases, from ESRF to FCC-ee $t\bar{t}$ energy. The linear flux density are also reported in the bottom part of the figure.

photon energies above the Z phase at 45.6 GeV beam energy. The ESRF has also a larger linear photon flux density and power. To deal with this, the ESRF intercepts in a very efficient way most of the dipole SR using so called “crotch absorbers”, which unfortunately cannot be implemented in a twin-ring accelerator like the FCC-ee due to geometrical constraints.

One can immediately notice that as soon as the energy of the FCC-ee is increased from 45.6 GeV the corresponding critical energy ε_c raises immediately above 100 keV. This photon energy range corresponds to very penetrating gamma rays, which can easily pass through any material over rather large thicknesses, in addition to creating diffuse electron and photon showers via Compton scattering. In fact, such photons can be used to carry out industrial gammagraphies, e.g. looking through thick metal sheets. For accelerators, this is very detrimental, as it can generate a large “leaking” field of hard photons outside of the vacuum chamber, which can irradiate the tunnel and all its components, activating materials and damaging them.

The design of the FCC-ee arc vacuum system must therefore consider this in order to assure the multi-decade-long experimental program and guarantee an acceptable integrated radiation dose to personnel accessing the tunnel.

4. The FCC-ee arc vacuum system

Since the inception of the FCC study program, many different versions and options of the FCC-ee arc vacuum system have been considered. After close scrutiny of the unique high-intensity and high-energy spectrum of the SR fan generated along the orbits, we have concluded that the most efficient way to deal with it is to implement a series of SR photon absorbers placed at carefully studied locations so as to intercept all primary SR photons (i.e. those which are not reflected or scattered). This solution guarantees the fastest beam conditioning, namely the fastest reduction of gas molecules desorbed per impinging photon. This is regularly experienced in all existing SR light sources where short localized SR photon absorbers have been used for dec-

Fig. 4: Pressure profiles in the FCC-ee main rings nearby a collision point. Black line: uncoated beam pipe; other colours: NEG coated beam pipe. The curves are calculated for four different gas flows extracted by SR from the adsorbers. The pressure peaks correspond to the position of the SR adsorbers. The average pressures are reported on the right side of the graph. On the left, a schematic of the two colliding rings. In red: e^- ; in grey: e^+ . Only the area inside the dashed rectangle is shown on the pressure plots.

ades. This also helps in localizing the source of high-energy Compton electron and photon cascades, as identified by detailed beam-material interaction modelling [13]. Without SR absorbers, the SR fan would hit the internal wall of the vacuum chamber along a continuous strip, as it happened to LEP, and this would require a continuous shielding with lead or other high atomic-number material, such as tungsten for instance. For an accelerator with 2 rings of ~ 91 km this would call for a large amount of shielding material, with attendant tunnel integration issues (e.g., supports).

Detailed ray-tracing monte-carlo simulations [14] have been carried out on 3D models of the vacuum chamber with SR absorbers; the location of SR absorbers along a sample 130 m-long section of the arcs, taken as representative, have been optimized. The resulting average longitudinal spacing of the absorbers is 5.5 m. The corresponding pressure profiles stemming from the SR-induced degassing have been calculated for various impinged photon doses, i.e. the integrated SR photon irradiation onto each point around the ring. The same pressure profiles, calculated for different gas species (typically H_2 , CO , CO_2 and CH_4) have been iteratively used as input in calculation of bremsstrahlung due to inelastic collisions between high-energy electrons and residual gas atoms [13].

Fig. 4 shows the results of pressure profile simulations along 300 m of one of the two colliding beam paths (the other one is symmetric) for CO gas, under different assumptions for the vacuum chamber material and its conditioning time.

black and orange curves). NEG coatings were developed at CERN in the late nineties to ensure uniformly distributed pumping speed in the LHC; such a coating is made of Ti, Zr and V co-sputtered from intertwined elemental cathodes, and their typical thicknesses are in the range 0.1 to $2 \mu m$ [15]. Heating at temperatures above $180^\circ C$ during the bakeout results in the dissolution of the coating oxide layer which, consequently, enable chemisorption on the film surface. The oxide reduction, in addition to pumping, ensure a very low SR-induced desorption [16] and a reduced secondary electron emission [17]. The industrial implementation of NEG coatings in 180 km of beam pipes is a real challenge and requires an intense technological development.

A strong program of design, prototyping and testing for the SR absorbers has been already set up: after trying several versions, we have come up with a novel design based on 3D printing technology, which allows us to optimize the cooling efficiency and keep the surface temperature at the location where the SR fan intercepts the absorber within safe limits

Fig. 5: 3D model of the SR adsorber. The SR light strikes on the inner face of the adsorber that is cooled by water. Such an element is welded to the beam pipe. The 3D drawing on the right show the temperature distribution on the surface of the adsorber; the maximum temperature is around $40^\circ C$. Courtesy of M. Morrone, S. Rorison, C. Garion, and F. Santangelo (CERN).

for the material chosen. The material we are considering is a copper alloy, either OFE Cu or CuCrZr. A 2 m-long prototype of extruded chamber with one SR absorber joined to it via electron-beam welding is under fabrication: it will be tested on the BESTEX SR beamline [18] of the 2.5 GeV KARA light source at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Karlsruhe, Germany.

Different views of the 3D-printed SR adsorber are shown on Fig. 5. The dashed red arrows represent the SR fan. On the right a thermal analysis based on the raytracing of SR.

As we plan to apply NEG coating to all the chambers, only a small number of pumps for H_2 , CO, CO_2 are necessary. Pumping CH_4 and any other ‘non-getterable’ gas specie (e.g., argon given off by TIG welds or small air leaks) will be left to ancillary sputter ion pumps placed along the arcs and connected via carefully designed pumping domes. We plan to minimize the number of these sputter ion pumps because they need high-voltage coaxial cables which are known to be subject to radiation damage in the tunnel of accelerators such as FCC-ee. Preliminary calculations done by a dedicated working group, R2E ‘Radiation to Electronics’, show that all sputter ion pump power supplies and other electronics must be placed in dedicated alcoves dug along the tunnel. The preliminary design calls for an alcove spacing of 1.6 km, i.e. each alcove will collect cables and host electronics for equipment 800 m upstream and 800 m downstream of its position.

The proposed FCC-ee vacuum chamber is a 70 (or 60) mm circular tube with two small ‘winglets’ in the plane of the orbit, with 10 mm height and total horizontal width of 115 mm (see Fig. 6), to install the SR absorbers and intercept SR. This vacuum chamber is made of cold-extruded OFE copper in up to 12 m long units. Our present development focuses on three key subjects for cost containment: the flanges and their vacuum tightness, the incorporation of heating elements for the bakeout, and the integration of beam position monitors (BPM).

Fig. 6: The proposed FCC-ee vacuum chamber extrusion placed on top of the extruded aluminium cross-section used for LEP (with external Pb shielding to stop high-energy radiation leakage). Courtesy of S. Rorison (CERN).

In the first development we profit of a recent development that successfully introduced shape-memory alloys (SMA) in vacuum technology for particle accelerators [19]. The properties of such materials, shaped as rings, can be utilized to tighten circular flanges simply by heating them; the unclamping is obtained by cooling the SMA rings to temperatures well below 0 °C. The circular flanges at the extrem-

ities of the chambers would be friction stir welded to the beampipe.

The second development concerns bakeout, which is an essential step in the process of achieving ultrahigh vacuum. However, the preparation for the bakeout is time consuming and represents an important workload; furthermore, standard heating jackets are expensive and can be deteriorated by radiation. To circumvent such hindrances, cold spray of heating circuits on the vacuum chamber are studied. This additive manufacturing comprises first the deposition of a thin electrical insulator and then of a resistive metal.

Finally, in the third development, the integration of about 8000 BPM is addressed. The present study considers BPM blocks directly added and finely machined on the vacuum chamber by additive technologies. Each BPM electrode would be tightly connected to the BPM block by a SMA ring.

5. The FCC-ee machine-detector interfaces and their vacuum system

The proper design of the vacuum system within the MDI (Machine Detector Interface) is critical for the FCC-ee collider. Its significance lies in ensuring minimal detector background, reducing radiation damage to detectors, accelerator components, and tunnel structures. This also includes mitigating radioactive activation to facilitate safe intervention by technical personnel in line with the ALARA principle (As Low As Reasonably Achievable).

The design of the MDI area leverages on prior experience with LEP, up to 104 GeV, and with data from more recent high-intensity B-factories such as the KEKB and SuperKEKB e^-e^+ colliders in Japan [20]. Given the extremely high beam energies, the FCC-ee’s MDI is affected by various forms of radiation, as well as collision debris. The former include bremsstrahlung, radiative Bhabha-scattered gamma rays, beam-gas scattering (elastic and inelastic), beam-thermal radiation scattering, SR from focusing/defocusing quadrupole doublets, and SR from intense solenoidal fields (2 T) within the detector. Most of the electromagnetic radiation generated by these five different effects is concentrated in a rather narrow conical space of $1/\gamma$ radians angular aperture, where γ is the relativistic factor of the beam. For the Z-energy phase, at 45.6 GeV, $\gamma = 89237$; for the $t\bar{t}$ it is 4 times higher. These values correspond to opening angle of the emission cone of about 1 cm diameter at 50 m distance. The total power contained within this narrow cone is of the order of several hundred kW (Z phase): it will require a very detailed study of a dedicated radiation beam dump line, similar to the one installed on each of the LHC beams, with a large-volume photon absorber inside a heavy radiation-shielded bunker. Due to the very large radius of curvature of the machine, about 10 km, a suitable horizontal separation of the e^-e^+ rings and the radiation beam dump will be attained only at about 500 m distance from the IP, meaning that the tunnel over this distance will have to be much larger than the regular arc tunnel, about 18 m wide horizontally instead of 5.5 m diameter along the arcs.

SR from the dipoles immediately upstream of the IP are taken care of by placing discrete absorbers at relevant positions, of the same type as described earlier for the arc

vacuum system, plus one last mask absorber in front of the first superconducting focusing quadrupole. A small fraction of this SR hits the internal part of the beryllium chamber, 180 mm long, around which the “vertex” detector layers are placed. These vertex detectors determine with high precision the exact point of impact of the colliding e^- and e^+ bunches. Only very low-energy SR photons are able reach the Be chamber, namely those generated at large angles. A thin layer of gold will be deposited on the internal wall of the Be chamber in order to prevent these SR photons from reaching the vertex detector.

Detailed ray-tracing simulations of the SR fans have been carried out with the SYNRAD+ Montecarlo code [21], to determine the distribution of the SR photons finally being absorbed along the MDI. These photon maps are then imported into the other raytracing Montecarlo code Molflow+ where the molecular flow stemming from photon-stimulated desorption is used as an input. Detailed 3-D models generated by CAD programs can be imported into both SYNRAD+ and Molflow+. These two software tools are being used since a decade or so by basically all accelerator laboratories and projects. They have been tested and validated within reasonable accuracies over a number of recent accelerators, most notably the 4th-generation light sources MAX-4 and SIRIUS.

Some codes used to design the MDI trace not only the SR photons but also all other forms of radiation, like scattered high-energy e^- and e^+ , plus the collision debris coming out of the interaction point. The multi-purpose code GEANT4 is usually used, in addition to FLUKA: these codes use models not only of the vacuum chamber but also of all detector components, estimating the radiation dose delivered to them.

For the design of the vacuum system of the MDI, we consider applying the same vacuum chamber cross-section concept with localised SR adsorbers as adopted along the arcs. A number of pumping ports are also placed either in front of each adsorber or immediately before it. Emphasis

is placed into the design of the “X”-shaped central chamber, where the e^- and e^+ beams’ paths cross at the 30 milliradians crossing angle (see Fig. 7), and eventually collide inside the short central beampipe.

This chamber is entirely placed inside the detector, and therefore needs to be transparent enough to the collision debris so as not to intercept and absorb too much of it. For this reason, the central ± 2 m long part is made of beryllium and its alloy Albemet, an Al-Be metal matrix composite [22]. The mechanical tolerances of this chamber are very stringent, in particular there is a very narrow space available for the chamber of the outgoing beam and the internal wall of the toroidal luminometer (LumiCal on Fig. 7), a very important device which measures the instantaneous luminosity of the collider. A close collaboration with the experimental physicists designing the detector components placed near the IP chamber is therefore mandatory. A dedicated series of meetings has been set up and run for several years already.

Moving away from the IP, in both directions, the central chamber is welded to aluminium-to-stainless steel transitions which allow welding of stainless steel-made bellows with RF contact fingers. The internal surface of these chambers is carefully designed and studied using sophisticated numerical modelling of its electromagnetic properties, using codes such as CST Studio, to avoid trapping of standing waves generated by the electromagnetic interaction of the intense e^-e^+ beams and the conductive chamber walls. Around the IP, over few meters of their length, both the e^- and e^+ beams transit inside the same chamber, in opposite directions, therefore doubling the beam current and complicating the image current calculations. Very small grid meshes are needed for these calculations, and this pushes to the limit the electromagnetic computations that sometimes require days of continuous processing prior to converging to a solution.

Fig. 7: Computer-generated view of 1 of 2 final focus superconducting quadrupole cryostat; the two counter-rotating beams collide at an angle of 30 milliradians (1.72°) inside the 180 mm long Be central chamber. Courtesy F. Franesini, INFN Frascati and CERN [22]

6. Conclusions

The Future Circular Collider (FCC-ee) highlights the indispensable nature of advanced vacuum technology in driving the frontiers of particle physics. Even if we have already identified conceptual solutions for the vacuum system of this accelerator, the unprecedented scale of this potential project underlines the necessity for a tight collaboration with the industry, emphasizing the critical role it plays in developing manufacturing processes. The success of FCC-ee relies on employing cutting-edge technology to mitigate radiation effects and ensure reliable operational standards while optimizing production processes to ensure affordable costs and

realistic planning. This alliance aims to address the complex challenges posed by big science equipment, necessitating a harmonized effort between scientific activities and industrial expertise.

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Appendix

Physics case:

Precision Measurements of the Higgs Boson Properties:

One of the primary goals of the FCC-ee is to conduct precise measurements of the properties of the Higgs boson. By colliding electrons and positrons at extremely high energies, scientists can study the Higgs boson with unparalleled precision. This includes measuring its mass, spin, and interaction strengths, providing deeper insights into the fundamental nature of this elusive particle and its role in the Standard Model of particle physics.

Testing the Standard Model and Searching for New Physics:

The FCC-ee serves as a powerful tool to scrutinize the predictions of the Standard Model of particle physics. While the Standard Model has been remarkably successful in explaining the known particles and their interactions, it is not a complete theory and leaves questions unanswered. By precisely measuring known particles and their behaviours, FCC-ee aims to identify any deviations from the Standard Model predictions, which could be indicative of new, previously undiscovered physics.

Study of Electroweak Processes:

Electroweak processes, which involve the interplay of electromagnetic and weak nuclear forces, are of particular interest in understanding the fundamental forces governing particles. FCC-ee's high-luminosity collisions provide an ideal environment for studying these processes with

unprecedented precision. This includes investigations into electroweak symmetry breaking and the properties of W and Z bosons.

Tau-Charm Physics and Flavour Factories:

The FCC-ee is designed to be a "flavour factory," producing copious amounts of tau leptons and charm quarks. By focusing on the study of these particles, scientists can delve into the realm of flavour physics, exploring the subtle differences in the behaviour of particles and their antimatter counterparts. This research can contribute to our understanding of CP violation and the matter-antimatter asymmetry observed in the universe.

Energy consumption:

To gauge the electrical energy usage per person among CERN Member States, we analyse the overall electricity consumption of the FCC and allocate it based on the total population. Assuming the FCC consumes 1 TWh annually and the collective population of CERN Member States is around 540 million. Hence, roughly 1.85 kWh per person would support the FCC annually. In comparison, household electricity consumption per person in the EU in 2021 averaged 1.7 MWh (sourced from Eurostat 2021). Thus, the electricity utilized per person for the FCC constitutes a relatively small portion of an individual's usual electricity usage. When spread across Member States, the FCC's electricity consumption stands as a reasonable and justified investment considering its contributions to global scientific, technological, and educational advancements.

Paolo Chiggiato serves as the head of the Vacuum, Surfaces, and Coatings group at CERN. With 35 years of experience at CERN, he has specialized in vacuum and material technology for high-energy particle accelerators, encompassing surface treatments. Currently, he is actively engaged in overseeing the operation of CERN's accelerator vacuum systems, contributing to the LHC upgrade, and participating in CERN's forthcoming initiatives such as FCC and muon colliders. Simultaneously, he participates in the design and prototyping of future gravitational wave telescopes. Specifically, he leads CERN's efforts on the Einstein Telescope's laser beam pipes. Additionally, he frequently provides valuable counsel on projects where vacuum systems hold critical significance.

Roberto Kersevan has spent 36 years working on vacuum for particle accelerators and thermonuclear fusion. He has been head of the vacuum group at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility in Grenoble, France, and has worked at 5 other laboratories in Italy and United States. He is consultant and reviewer for many international projects. He is mostly known for having started and leading development of the monte carlo raytracing code Molflow+ which is used by basically all accelerator laboratories and space industry as well. Frequent lecturer at gas dynamics schools and workshops.

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